

ISSUES OF MANAGING THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF REGIONS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8223459>

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Abstract

his article discusses the regions of our country, the organization of their effective management, indicators of the socio-economic assessment of the regions, additional measures and parameters for the integrated socio-economic development of the regions of the Bukhara region in 2022-2026. and further improvement of the standard of living of the population, proposals and recommendations for the development of the region's economy are highlighted.

Keywords

socio-economic environment, degree of effectiveness, planning and forecasting, globalization and internationalization, regional economy, digital economy, gross regional product, "growth points", "driver areas".

The modern socio-economic environment in the regions of Uzbekistan has been undergoing dramatic changes over the past decades, primarily related to the development of information and financial services, the digital economy, with inclusion in the provision of world economic relations, with increased requirements for the very structure of the economy and for the formation of an infrastructure environment. The degree of effectiveness of these transformations is determined by the current management system and its compliance with the achievement of the formulated goals and priorities for the development of society. At the same time, it should be noted that the current management model should adequately take into account the peculiarities of the Uzbek regions - their natural and climatic conditions, different initial levels of socio-economic development, investment climate and different opportunities to adapt to market relations. Therefore, the development of a general concept for managing the socio-economic development of regions of all ranks is of particular relevance, since the effectiveness of the management system at the regional and municipal levels determines the

competitiveness of the regions and the conditions for business development and the life of the population.

The inefficiency of the country's regions of the management system, which for a long time was compensated by high prices for fuel and energy resources on the world market, was clearly revealed with their sharp fall.

It is known that a necessary attribute of the process of social reproduction is its continuity, which is ensured by the continuity of the management process, which creates conditions for the constant renewal of information and material and financial flows, and, accordingly, the development of the economy and people's livelihoods. If we briefly characterize the essence of the management system from the position of the theory of reproduction, then it can be defined as the justification and adoption of planning and forecast decisions that determine the current and long-term trajectory of the socio-economic development of the country and its regions, and the creation of channels for their implementation.

As practice shows, the mandatory elements of managing socio-economic development, necessary in order to ensure the continuity of management, and, accordingly, the continuity of the process of social reproduction, are:

Improving the efficiency of regional development management based on the cluster approach. One of the most important functions of regional management is to ensure effective spatial development based on the use of the resource potential of the entire territory.

The role of the management system in realizing the region's competitive advantages. The transition to market relations has led to the fact that not only

enterprises, but also regions are in a tough competitive environment. Competition finds its manifestation, first of all, in the struggle to attract qualified specialists and investment resources. If during the period of industrial development of the economy the main competitive advantage of the region was the availability of raw materials, then at the present stage of post-industrial development the most prosperous countries and regions are those that have a large share of personnel with high human capital in the structure of labor resources.

It is known that competition is the essence of market relations and the main factor determining the state of the regional economy, which develops according to the laws of the market. The very content of the competitive advantages of the regions is changing under the influence of the processes taking place in the world economy, among which the following should be noted:

- intensive development of science and high technology, innovative industries, digital economy. The action of these processes has led to the fact that the competitive advantages of the regions began to be determined not by the presence of traditional production factors, but by the position of the region in the use of innovative opportunities;

- globalization and internationalization of regional systems. At the present stage of development of the world economy, transnational integration, interregional and international redistribution of investments is clearly manifested, which changes the resource potential of the region and its competitive advantages. In the context of the globalization of the world economy, when the issues of division of labor and the development of integration ties are resolved within the framework of transnational companies, it is futile to develop strategies for individual regions and municipalities;

- formation of new elements of the market infrastructure. Particularly strong changes are taking place in the development of market infrastructure. Banking and wholesale and retail networks come to the fore, which stimulate the development of horizontal links between producers and consumers of products. And, finally, the normal functioning of the market largely depends on reliable information and legal support, which is associated with arbitration consideration of various issues and with qualified legal registration of transactions;

- Strengthening state regulation of the regional economy. The content of state regulation of market processes at the regional level, its forms and methods are determined, on the one hand, by domestic economic policy, and, on the other hand, are influenced by global trends and patterns of socio-economic development.

Tendencies towards strengthening state regulation of the market are noted by many economists.

As a result of the strengthening of the role of the information factor in the development of the modern economy, a wide variety of institutions are being formed that take part in the regulation of market processes.

An analysis of world experience and current trends in the development of the economy shows that prosperous regions are characterized by the priority development of knowledge-intensive industries, market infrastructure and services based on innovation and information technology. The priority development of these areas of the region's economy allows to significantly increase the volume of the gross regional product, tax revenues to the regional budget, ensure a high level of employment, improve the standard of living of the population and the competitiveness of the region's economy.

Our country adopted a resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 on the comprehensive socio-economic development of the districts of the Bukhara region and additional measures to further improve the living standards of the population.

Based on the new order of integrated socio-economic development of the regions, the existing problems and opportunities in the districts and cities of the Bukhara region were studied in depth, important projects were formed in the region, and the participation of the local community was established. is widely discussed.

In Bukhara region in 2022-2026, the volume of gross regional product will increase by 1,4 times, the volume of industrial output by 1,5 times, agricultural production by 1,2 times, the volume of services by 3,1 times, the volume of construction work by 1,5 times the parameters of target indicators in the context of cities and districts were approved, providing for an increase in.¹⁴²

Table-1

Target indicators for comprehensive socio-economic development of Bukhara region in 2022-2026

PARAMETERS

Indicators	Unit of measure	total	over the years				
			2022	2023	2024	2025	2026
Gross domestic product,	trln. soum	1.4 times	42,3	48,8	56,2	64,6	73,6

¹⁴² <https://lex.uz/docs/-5988275>

per capita	million soums		21,3	24,3	27,6	31,3	35,2
Industrial product	trln. soum	1,5 times	22,3	25,4	29,5	34,6	40,8
per capita	million soums		11,2	12,6	14,5	16,7	19,5
Agriculture	trln. soum	1,2 times	30,1	31,1	32,4	33,9	35,6
per capita	million soums		5,1	15,4	15,7	16,2	16,8
Increasing "green areas":							
establishment of green areas in the regions	thousand hectares	146,8	71,8	35,0	20,0	10,0	10,0
creation of public parks and green spaces in city and district centers	hectares	60,2	60,2	-	-	-	-
planting trees and ornamental shrubs	million pieces	54259	10042	10617	10700	11800	11100
Household waste processing	percentage	61,8	49	55	61	69	75

Based on the above, specialization of cities and districts of Bukhara region, "growth points" and "driver areas" were determined.¹⁴³

Table 2

No	The name of the areas	"Growth points" and "driver areas" of districts (cities)
1.	Bukhara city	Development of tourism and textile industries
2.	Kogon city	Development of construction materials industry and tourism
3.	Bukhara district	Development of greenhouse and animal husbandry sectors
4.	Vobkent district	Development of animal husbandry and horticulture
5.	Jondor district	Development of poultry and food industries
6.	Kogon district	Development of greenhouse and building materials industries
7.	Olot district	Development of livestock and poultry industries
8.	Peshku district	Development of greenhouse and animal husbandry sectors
9.	Romitan district	Development of greenhouse and textile industries
10.	Shafirkon district	Development of horticulture and building materials industries
11.	Karakol district	Development of greenhouses, leather processing industries
12.	Qarovulbazar district	Development of animal husbandry and horticulture

¹⁴³ <https://lex.uz/docs/-5988275>

13.	Gijduvan district	Development of building materials industry and food industry
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Despite the implementation of the above decisions and programs, the level of poverty in some regions remains high. We would like to give a number of suggestions and recommendations in order to ensure the employment of the population and facilitate the access of privileged resources.

Based on the above analysis, we would like to make the following proposals to stabilize the main macroeconomic indicators and achieve economic growth in the Bukhara region in 2023-2024:

1. All measures must be taken to support initiatives and new projects of the private sector in networks and to develop cooperation. It is necessary to reduce the participation of the state in investment policy and increase the share of private and direct investment. The area has the possibility of more favorable conditions for the development of entrepreneurship and small businesses.

2. The priority will be to increase the income per hectare of land from the current average of \$22400 to at least \$587000. To do this, it is necessary to widely introduce into agriculture the most advanced technologies, water-saving and biotechnologies, the achievements of seed production, science and innovation.

3. First of all, it is necessary to increase the interest of farmers and peasants in the land. Where there is interest and justice, there is bound to be change and growth. In this regard, the time has come to consider the issue of guaranteeing land use rights and turning land into a commodity asset.

4. Revision of the tourism potential of the Bukhara region, revision of its historical and cultural heritage, reconstruction of the shrines of "Kiz Bibi" and the shrines of Mahmud Tarobi, review of historical sources and search for new sources.

5. Having considered the peculiarities of cooking in the Bukhara region, we need to determine its differences from other regions. On this basis, it is necessary to develop ways to attract tourists.

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